

THE GRAMOPHONE: A PROGRAMMABLE DMI TO FACILITATE THE TEACHING OF STEM DISCIPLINES

Romain MICHON (michon@grame.fr)^{1,2}, Catinca DUMITRASCU¹, Stéphane LETZ¹, Yann ORLAREY¹, and Dominique FOBER¹

¹GRAME, Centre National de Création Musicale, Lyon, France

²Center for Computer Research in Music and Acoustics (CCRMA), Stanford University, CA USA

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce the Gramophone, a Digital Musical Instrument programmable with the FAUST programming language. The Gramophone has been designed as part of the Amstramgrame project which aims at facilitating the teaching of STEM disciplines through audio programming. The Gramophone is completely standalone and it hosts a wide range of sensors to control sound synthesis parameters. Its programming is carried out through a pedagogical web platform. A total of 160 Gramophones were produced as part of Amstramgrame and are now touring in French public schools. This paper presents the design process that led to this instrument, its implementation and evaluation, as well as future directions for this work.

1. INTRODUCTION

STEAM¹ projects have become popular in recent years, taking different approaches combining the teaching of Sciences with the Arts. The field of music technology has been acting as a natural platform for the development of this type of project [1–4]. *iMuSciCA* [5] is very representative by aiming at facilitating the teaching of sciences through music technology via a Web platform [6] where students can design their own musical instruments using physics and mathematics principles, visualize the physical parameters of a sound in the prospect of making a composition, etc.

While most STEAM projects in the field of music technology focus on the combination of Sciences with the Arts, fewer emphasize computer programming. In that context, we recently launched the Amstramgrame project² [7] which aims at facilitating the teaching of maths and physics through the programming of a physical Digital Musical Instrument (DMI): the Gramophone (see Figure 1).

The Amstramgrame website plays a central role serving both as:

¹ Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics

² <https://www.amstramgrame.fr/>

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Figure 1. The Gramophone.

- a pedagogical platform for teachers and students providing pre-written lessons,
- an environment to program the Gramophone.

A typical Amstramgrame module begins with a maths or physics teacher, leads to the development of an audio DSP algorithm that in turn, is used to program the Gramophone to make a custom musical instrument. Finally, students work with a composer to improve their instrument and to write a piece that is performed by the class during a final performance.

The Gramophone was specifically developed for Amstramgrame to provide a platform to make the programming of audio DSP³ algorithms (and hence, of mathematical concepts studied in class) more tangible. It is lightweight, completely standalone (it hosts a built-in rechargeable lithium battery and a speaker), robust, and it can be programmed using the FAUST programming language⁴ [8] through a web platform. A 9 DoF motion sensor as well as a physical button and rotary potentiometers can be used to control the parameters of the synthesized sound. The Gramophone was designed to be held in one hand and can be easily moved around by the performer thanks to its strap (see Figure 1).

In this paper, we first present the early prototypes of the Gramophone that led to its final design. We then describe

³ Digital Signal Processing

⁴ <https://faust.grame.fr>

the hardware and software implementation of this instrument before providing information on its diffusion as well as the results of an evaluation conducted on about 180 students and over 160 gramophones. We finally reflect upon future directions for this project.

2. EARLY PROTOTYPES

The development of the Gramophone was initiated in January 2019. We wanted this instrument to meet a certain number of requirements by being:

- standalone (e.g., battery powered and host a built-in speaker),
- programmable with FAUST,
- playable with one hand,
- quick at booting,
- robust and durable (and hence adapted to primary and middle school students).

Given the size constraints, the immediate boot time, and portability requirements, we decided to build this instrument around a microcontroller powerful enough to carry out real-time audio DSP. The best candidate at the time was the Teensy 3.6,⁵ which provided unparalleled computational power (180 MHz) and support for real-time audio processing through the Teensy audio library⁶ as well as an “audio shield”⁷ (audio codec sister board). In that context, we implemented *faust2teensy* [9], a command line tool allowing for the programming of the Teensy with FAUST for real-time audio DSP applications.

Our initial prototype (see Figure 2) was designed to be held as a stick and looked a little bit like a rattle (or a pan). The only continuous controller was a 9 DoF motion sensor as well as a button mounted on the handle of the instrument. Its shape potentially limited the orientation that could be given to the object and mobilized all the fingers of the hand to hold the device.

The second iteration of the Gramophone (see Figure 3) solved this issue and gave access to a joystick that could be controlled by the thumb of the hand holding the instrument. A photoresistor was also added to the handle.

Both designs implied the use of an external battery charging circuit (“battery boost”) connected to the Teensy as well as a small amplifier for the speaker. The battery boost tended to create ground issues with the Teensy resulting into background noise. All in all, we hoped for a all-in-one solution where the microcontroller, the motion sensor, the amplifier, and the battery charging circuit could all be integrated in the same board. This was a big concern since we were planning on making a fairly large number of Gramophones for Amstramgrame (we were thinking of at least 100 at the time), so the design had to be as optimized as possible.

⁵ <https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy36.html>

⁶ https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/td_libs_Audio.html

⁷ https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy3_audio.html

Figure 2. The initial prototype of the Gramophone.

3. THE GRAMOPHONE

3.1 Overview

Only a few months after the first Gramophone prototypes were completed, LilyGO released a new ESP-32 based board: the TTGO TAudio.⁸ For only \$15, this board hosts an ESP-32 microcontroller (with built-in WiFi and Bluetooth and a dual core processor operating at 240 MHz), a 9 DoF motion sensor, a battery charging circuit, and an audio codec with a built-in amplifier. We therefore saw it as a way to solve many technical problems that we had with using the Teensy to make our instrument. In that context, we developed *faust2esp32* [10], a command line tool to program ESP32 based boards with FAUST, making this language the only alternative to C++ to program this platform.

The final version of the Gramophone is built around a LilyGO TTGO TAudio board (see Figure 4 for the initial prototype of the final version, Figure 1 for the final distributed version, and Figure 6 for a detailed view of the different features of the Gramophone). It fits in one hand and can be easily moved around thanks to its strap. A photoresistor lands directly under the thumb of the performer. Similarly, a button finds its place under the middle finger. A rotary potentiometer can be controlled with the left hand of the performer. The Gramophone benefits directly from the built-in 9 DoF sensor of the TTGO TAudio board. All these sensors can be assigned to sound synthesis parameters directly from the FAUST program (see §4).

The Gramophone is charged and programmed through a micro USB cable which connects to the corresponding port on the TTGO TAudio board. A 2.05 Ah lithium battery ensures an extended autonomy for the Gramophone which

⁸ <http://www.lilygo.cn/>

Figure 3. The second prototype of the Gramophone.

Figure 4. The third prototype of the Gramophone.

can be played for about 24 hours in battery mode (with a standard use). A microphone can be used to process sound in real-time. A dedicated rotary potentiometer can be used to control the volume of the instrument. Finally, a rotary encoder allows the performer to cycle around different FAUST programs installed on the Gramophone.

3.2 The Gramophone Case

The Gramophone case was entirely designed in OpenScad⁹ and Inkscape¹⁰ (through Inkscape2scad¹¹). Since we never intended to sell the Gramophone, we wanted to make sure that it could easily be reproduced (and/or modified) using tools accessible to everyone. The source files of the Gramophone case as well as the corresponding STL

⁹<https://www.openscad.org/>

¹⁰<https://inkscape.org/>

¹¹<https://github.com/grame-cncm/faust/tree/master-dev/tools/physicalModeling/inkscape2scad>

files can be found on the Amstramgrame GitHub.¹² Since a large number of Gramophones had to be made for Amstramgrame (over 160), the 3D printing of their case was outsourced.

3.3 Electronics and Assembly

Beside its TTGO TAudio board, the Gramophone relies on fairly simple electronic components (i.e., speaker, battery, potentiometers, buttons, etc.). An exhaustive video tutorial on how to assemble a Gramophone can be found on the Amstramgrame website.¹³ Assembling a Gramophone from scratch takes about three hours. To make the 160 Gramophones of Amstramgrame, we hired an “assembler” for a period of five months whose role was also to test each Gramophone before shipping.

4. SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENT

4.1 Programming Environment

The Amstramgrame website contains dozens of Gramophone program examples spread across a wide range of tutorials. Each example can be edited in a simplified version of the FAUST Web IDE [11] specifically designed as part of Amstramgrame.¹⁴ The sound corresponding to a Gramophone FAUST program can be heard and prototyped directly in the web browser. A “Gramo” button can be pressed to generate the firmware corresponding to the FAUST program ready-to-be-installed on the Gramophone.

The GramoLoader¹⁵ (see Figure 8) is a software tool designed as part of Amstramgrame acting as a bridge between the FAUST Web IDE and the Gramophone. It takes the firmware generated when pressing the “Gramo” button and installs it on the Gramophone. Once the firmware has been selected once, it will be automatically installed

¹²<https://github.com/amstramgrame/amstramgrame>

¹³<https://www.amstramgrame.fr/en/gramophone/making/>

¹⁴<https://faustide.grame.fr/?mode=amstram>

¹⁵<https://www.amstramgrame.fr/gramophone/loader/>

Figure 5. Overview of the components of the Gramophone.

Figure 6. The various elements of the Gramophone.

Figure 7. The Amstramgrame FAUST Web IDE.

Figure 8. The GramoLoader.

on the Gramophone every time the “Gramo” button will be pressed. The GramoLoader is written in Python, is available for Windows, MacOS, and Linux, and it is completely open source.

4.2 Programming the Gramophone

4.2.1 Mapping Controllers to DSP Parameters

A Gramophone program can be as simple as:

```
import ("stdfaust.lib");
f = hslider("freq[knob:2]",
  440, 50, 1000, 0.01) : si.smoo;
t = button("gate[switch:1]") : si.smoo;
process = os.osc(f)*gate;
```

In that case, the frequency of a sine wave oscillator is controlled by the rotary potentiometer of the Gramophone and sound can be triggered by pressing the button under the middle finger. In other words, any FAUST parameter

(i.e., declared with a slider, a nentry, a button, etc.) can be mapped to a Gramophone controller using a metadata. Standard FAUST motion sensors (i.e., gyroscope, accelerometer, etc.) metadatas can be used to map the 9 DoF sensor of the Gramophone to FAUST parameters. An exhaustive list of the Gramophone FAUST metadata can be found on the Amstramgrame website.¹⁶

4.2.2 MIDI Bluetooth

MIDI Bluetooth support has recently been added to the Gramophone. A Bluetooth device name can be declared using the `btmidi_device_name` general metadata. Standard FAUST MIDI metadatas¹⁷ can then be used.

¹⁶ <https://www.amstramgrame.fr/gramophone/about/#metadatas-de-programmation-du-gramophone>

¹⁷ <https://faustdoc.grame.fr/manual/midi/>

In the following examples:

```
declare btmidi_device_name "Gramophone";
f = hslider("freq[midi: ctrl 0]",
  440, 50, 1000, 0.01) : si.smoo;
t = button("gate[switch:1]") : si.smoo;
process = os.osc(f)*gate;
```

the frequency parameter of the sine wave oscillator is controlled using MIDI CC 0 and sound is triggered by pressing the button on the Gramophone.

In the previous example, Bluetooth pairing has to be initiated by an external device (e.g., a smartphone, a computer, etc.) but the Gramophone itself can be configured to initiate pairing by specifying the name of the target with the `btmidi_remote_name` general metadata. E.g.:

```
declare btmidi_remote_name "External MIDI
  Keyboard";
```

This also can be used to connect two Gramophones together to potentially synchronize them, etc.

4.2.3 Limitations

The programming limitations of the Gramophone are directly linked to that of the TTGO TAudio board [10]. For instance, the limited amount of RAM (about 1MB) has a significant impact on the kind of DSP algorithms that can be ran on the Gramophone. For instance, long delays and echos or complex reverbs will likely not work on this instrument. The same is true for table-based oscillators, but the FAUST compiler now integrates a system to automatically adapt table sizes when using embedded systems requiring small memory footprints.

Computational power is less of an issue and the dual core processor of the TTGO TAudio board running at 240 MHz is powerful enough to run a wide range of DSP algorithms.

5. DIFFUSION AND EVALUATION

Over 160 Gramophones were produced as part of Amstramgramme to constitute “Gramophone backpacks” containing 30 Gramophones each. A “Gramophone assembler” was hired for a period of five months to carry out this task (see §3.3). All Gramophones are owned by the Amstramgramme project: we currently do not sell them since this would be too complicated for us from a legal standpoint.

The pilot phase of Amstramgramme (see Figure 9) ended in March 2021 and was carried out in two different schools, targeting a total of eight classes (middle and high school level) corresponding to about 180 students for a total of eighty hours of Amstramgramme sessions [7]. From a technical standpoint, the Gramophones and their tool-chain proved to be relatively stable. Only 4 Gramophones broke during this period (and were immediately and easily fixed). The web platform never stopped working and both students and instructors made positive comments about all the tools used as part of Amstramgramme. Gramophones ended up being adapted to most hands (large or small) and having satisfying ergonomics. A large number of users highlighted their good sound quality and loudness.

Figure 9. An Amstramgramme session at the *Cité scolaire du Cheylard* (Ardèche, France) – with social distancing.

Now that the pilot phase of the project is over, Amstramgramme will be implemented at a larger scale in a wide range of schools of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region in France. The scope of the project had to be slightly limited/adapted due to the Covid-19 pandemic though.

6. FUTURE WORK

At this point, we consider that the Gramophone reached a certain level of stability and we don’t plan to make any modifications to it in the future. However we do believe that its programming tool-chain could be improved. For instance, we would like to get rid of the GramoLoader to replace it with a system fully integrated in the Web browser (a bit like the Arduino Create Platform¹⁸). Indeed, the fact that the GramoLoader is platform-dependent and requires an installation can be a significant problem in schools that don’t have a permanent system administrator (which is often the case in France). Having a comprehensive web solution would solve this problem and make Amstramgramme more portable.

We’re currently working on an adapted version of the FAUST Playground¹⁹ allowing for the programming of the Gramophone. Unlike in the FAUST Web IDE, FAUST programs can be assembled using a graphical patching environment in the FAUST Playground, making it more accessible to younger students.

Our ambition is to add a hardware prototyping aspect to Amstramgramme by offering the possibility to substitute Gramophones with kits allowing students to make their own instrument using sensors and cardboard (in a similar way as Nitendo labo²⁰). The programming tool-chain would remain the same as for the Gramophones. The development of these kits was recently initiated.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Amstramgramme gave us the opportunity to (i) develop a DMI from scratch: the Gramophone, (ii) produce it at a fairly large scale, and (iii) evaluate its use by a large group

¹⁸ <https://create.arduino.cc/editor>

¹⁹ <https://faustplayground.grame.fr/>

²⁰ <https://labo.nintendo.com/>

of people. We believe that it fulfilled its initial objective which was to provide a platform to make more tangible the various scientific concepts approached in class in the context of Amstramgrame.

While the use of the Gramophones has been limited so far to pedagogical purposes, we plan to take advantage of the fact that we own a large number of them to use this instrument in the context of professional music productions to create a “Gramophone orchestra.”

Acknowledgments

The development of the Gramophone and of its programming tool-chain has been carried out as part of the Amstramgrame project which is funded by the métropole de Lyon, the DRAC Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, the SNCF foundation, and the Blaise Pascal foundation.

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